

Alva-Vista Crayfish Export
Business Plan Report for New Business Venture (NBV)
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1.0 Introduction

Alva-Vista Crayfish Export is an expanding enterprise located at 112 Road, Festac Town, Lagos, Nigeria. The company specialises in procuring and shipping premium crayfish, capitalising on Nigeria's abundant freshwater resources to cater to both domestic and international markets. The primary goal is to establish a robust presence in the global crayfish industry by offering expertly processed crayfish products renowned for their cleanliness, purity, and superior quality. The secondary objective comprises generating employment possibilities to decrease Nigeria's unemployment rate and conducting research and the utilisation of modernised technology in order to enhance crayfish productivity, thereby positioning Nigeria to take the lead as the highest producer of crayfish across the world, hence boosting the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

2.0 Overview of Nigeria's Crayfish Export Industry

The crayfish market on a global scale has experienced continuous growth driven by the high demand for seafood within various culinary applications of culinary (Expert Market, 2024). Nigeria's competitive advantage in the production of crayfish is proven with an estimated yearly output of 12,000 metric tonnes (Foraminifera, 2018). However, challenges like inconsistent quality and fragmented supply chain led to a negative impact on the potential growth of the industry.

In order to tackle these difficulties, Alva-Vista Crayfish Export intends to establish a vertically integrated business model that includes crayfish farming, processing, and export. By utilising advanced efficient logistics, aquaculture practices, and state of art processing facilities, the industry aims to implement a constant supply for premium crayfish globally. Carrying out a strategic partnership among farmers and other stakeholders will build the reliability of the overall quality of the supply chain of crayfish in Nigeria (Okeke & Nwankwo 2020).

Financial projections in the next five suggest an optimistic future for Alva-Vista Crayfish Export, with projected steady increase in supply across the globe which will consequently skyrocket the profit-making. In a few years' time, the company is expected to make a massive return of investments among those potential investors (WWF, 2019). These financial forecasts of the company are back through market analysis, operational strategy and risk management plan.

The market analysis indicates that the main target of crayfish exports are Nigerians and other Africans immigrants residing specifically in the United Kingdom, Canada and United States. These individuals are interested in purchasing crayfish needed while cooking their local dishes (Odili, 2019). Nigeria's substantial production volumes and advantageous pricing provide it with a competitive advantage in the worldwide market despite the fact of rivals from nearby countries such as Cameroon, Togo, Ghana and Senegal (Osabohien et al, 2019). Nevertheless, it is imperative to adopt more controlled and structured procedures in order to maximise Nigeria's capacity to export crayfish. This entails developing measures on safety and quality as well as enhancing transportation systems and logistics (Foraminifera, 2018).

Alva-Vista may position itself as a prominent exporter of crayfish in Nigeria compared to other competitors by taking priority of productivity, excellence and strategic collaboration. By addressing the problem that poses crayfish export industry the company can make a reasonable growth within the sector of agriculture, consequently leading to the increase of Nigeria Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and improve standard of living as more job opportunities will be created.

3.0 Contextual Analysis

3.1 SWOT Analysis

Alva-Vista operates in the agricultural landscape in Nigeria and is impacted by internal strengths and weaknesses as well as external opportunities and threats which shape the venture in the supply of crayfish.

Strength: Alva-Vista benefits from a robust local market which is deeply rooted by the traditional culinary of the country (Business Plan, 2020). Holding a dominant position in the home country market provides significant benefit by ensuring stable and dependable streams of revenue while also allowing the doors open for any potential growth in the future. Furthermore the company ensures that they make profit from different angles by selling its products not just abroad but within the country even though the main goal of the business is selling goods among international clients. So customers within Nigeria can also partake in enjoying the company products (Success, n.d.). And again as activities of the production of the crayfish take place in Nigeria there can be several benefits like creation of job opportunities within the country.

Weaknesses: Alva-Vista experience flows in its operational activities. A clear instance it's the vulnerability of crayfish availability in various seasons which poses a great threat to the company (Tran et al., 2021). This seasonal fluctuation of crayfish can disrupt supply chain schedules, which potentially lead to inefficiencies and revenue loss. In addition the limited shelf life of crayfish lead to logistics issues, which necessitate robust storage and distribution systems such as implementation of cold room storage and cold warehouse in order to maintain the freshness of the crayfish to preserve its taste (Prime Group, 2021).

Opportunities: Alva-Vista has several ranges of external prospects. As the company expands its production of crayfish across various countries, it generates more sales. The more the business

focuses on supply to various countries the more they have the opportunity to generate more revenue (Esheya, 2023). Furthermore there is a chance for the industry to introduce a wide range of products and introduce new ideas that will expand the business.

Threats: Alva-Vista also faces external threats that disrupt the achievement of the company and sustainability in the market. One main threat is intense competition from a well-established export industry and alternative seafood products (Trans et al, 2021). Furthermore, the need to adhere to export rules and regulations especially within Nigeria poses another challenge.

3.2 PESTLE Analysis

Political (Policy): The political stability and regulatory framework in Nigeria impact the operational activities of Alva-Vista since there can be changes in legislation, such as trade policies and regulations which can affect international trade, thereby potentially affect the exportation of goods. Additional government policies concerning customer loans can shape the market within the agriculture industry (Oyeranmi, 2023).

Economic (Economic): The present situations like devaluation of local currency, rapid rise of exchange rate, can have the effect of the increase in revenue of Alva-Vista as they supply crayfish across the world. The economic volatility in Nigeria can significantly influence borrowing, which in turn affects the decision to invest in processing facilities and transportation infrastructures (Udeze et al., 2021).

Social (Society): lifestyle choices, demography and core values have impact on both the demand and consumption of crayfish within a market. This social impact caused Alva-Visa to make adjustments of their price as they considered the income of individuals in a geographical region. Furthermore, the market perception of crayfish as a nutritious and sustainable food option may be impacted by social trends linked to environmental concern and health (Udeze et al., 2021).

Technological (Technology): The advancement of technology can ensure the increase in productivity of Alva-Vista crayfish (Ogah et al., 2022). For example, investments in research and development in the use of cutting edge technology for farming business such as reproductive techniques and genetics tools can consequently lead to enhanced breeding of crayfish.

Legal (Policy): Regulatory compliance requirements like National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) regulations, and International Trade law is essential for Alva-Vista to comply with their rules in order to operate the business legally. This adherence will ensure the integrity of the business product and build trust among the consumers (Oyeranmi, 2023).

Environmental (Ecology): Environmental factors, including water quality and climate change can have an effect on the habitat structure of crayfish which affects the harvest fields for Alva-Vista. Adverse weather conditions may disrupt the crayfish production cycles which will increase the challenges of operations of the business. Moreover, ecological considerations are importance in carrying out maintenance of the long-term sustainability of crayfish resources and mitigating environmental impacts that as to do with production and the activities of exporting (Maulu et al, 2023).

3.3 Ansoff Matrix

Adoption of Ansoff Matrix business model for Alva-Vista Crayfish Export to deal with product diversification and a systematic approach in expanding into existing markets (Yin, 2019). First, the company can impose market penetration strategy by increasing its efforts in existing markets, specifically targeting local buyers within Nigeria. This should be based on providing promotional support and strengthening customer loyalty to expand its business (Garba, 2024). Alva-Vista plans to use these activities to increase its visibility in the Nigerian crayfish market and increase its sales.

This may require expansion of crayfish products to other sizes or value added services such as the option of pre-cooked crayfish.

In addition, the adoption of market techniques can ensure the massive supply of Alva-Vista products outside of Nigeria. This may entail the supply of crayfish to a new global market where there is a need for premium crayfish. Finally, although diversification is a risk however Alva-Vista will still go ahead carrying this marketing strategy and for the business to overcome the such risk is by using analogous diversification tactics to expand its range of products in the fisheries industry. For instance the company could consider supplying other seafood goods like Crab rather than just focusing on crayfish.

3.4 Porter's Five Forces Analysis

- 1. Competition Among Established Companies:** The crayfish export sector in Nigeria experiences a moderate level of competition among well-established companies, as there are many competitors in the market and increasing demand both domestically and internationally (Daniel, 2023). Nevertheless Alva-Vista can overcome this challenges by leveraging strategic advantages like focusing on superior sourcing of crayfish where there is high quality of production of crayfish, emphasising on brand differentiation among other competitors and ensuring strict quality control procedure which includes meticulous packaging, processing and handling that preserve the quality and freshness of crayfish.
- 2. Potential Competitor Entry Threat:** The crayfish export sector in Nigeria has minimal risk of new competitors entering the market, primarily because there are substantial obstacles that deter potential entrants (Daniel, 2023). The obstacles encompass the need for significant financial resources, specialised expertise in crayfish farming and export protocols, established connections with suppliers and purchasers, and compliance with

stringent regulatory criteria. For Alva-Vista to overcome any new threat of competitors entering the crayfish export market in Nigeria, it could invest in specialised training for its employer in order for them to have rigorous expertise in export protocols and crayfish farming. It could also focus on strategic partnership among local buyers and suppliers, secure funding through various channels like government grant, business loan and investors and prioritise compliance with regulatory standards in order to build credibility and trust in the organisation.

3. **Supplier Bargaining Power:** The suppliers of crayfish in Nigeria hold a moderate degree of leverage in negotiations (Mind Tools, 2022). However Alva-Vista can restrict the number of suppliers by depending on specific places that are well-known for producing superior crayfish and dedicate itself on sustainable sourcing procedure and partnership with farmers to have direct supply of crayfish.
4. **Buyers Bargaining Power:** Just like the supplier the buyers in the global market can possess a significant degree of negotiating power (Mind Tools, 2022). This is influenced by various factors, including the presence of alternative products and the convenience of changing suppliers. Alva-Vista's emphasis on providing superior crayfish goods, together with its reputation for dependability and commitment to global quality benchmarks, can counterbalance buyer influence by fostering brand loyalty and distinctiveness.
5. **Substitute Product Threat:** Alva-Vista Crayfish Export has a moderate risk from substitute products, particularly from other sources of protein and seafood items (Chidmi et al, 2012). Nevertheless, the distinct flavour and consistency of Nigerian crayfish, together with Alva-Vista's dedication to excellence and environmental responsibility, can

counteract this risk by establishing a specialised market sector and cultivating consumer allegiance.

3.5 Business Canvas Model

Key Partners:	Key Activities:	Value Propositions:	Customer Relationships:	Customer Segments:
Local crayfish suppliers	Sourcing high-quality crayfish	Premium-grade, meticulously processed crayfish	Personalized customer service	Wholesalers, retailers, and food service providers
Packaging material suppliers	Processing, cleaning, and packaging	A reliable source of high-quality crayfish	Long-term partnerships	Individuals seeking premium crayfish products
Shipping and logistics companies	Ensuring export regulation compliance	Clean, well-prepared crayfish products	Integration with a business model	
Quality control agencies	Marketing and sales efforts			
	Key Resources:		Channels:	
	High-quality crayfish sources		Online platforms	
	Skilled labourer		Direct sales	
	Packaging materials		Export agents and distributors	
	Export licenses and permits			
	Marketing and sales team			
Cost Structure:		Revenue Streams		
Procurement of crayfish materials	Packaging	Sales revenue		
Shipping and logistics	Quality control	Export proceeds and foreign exchange		
Labor costs	Processing	Potential revenue from value-added services		

This business canvas model highlights the premium crayfish sourcing, export model, processing, and components of partnership, revenue streams and cost.

3.6 Strategic Alternatives and Analysis

Alva-Vista's decision to adopt Ansoff Matrix, SWOT analysis, PESTLE analysis, Business Model Canvas and Porter Five Forces analysis into the business plan is based on the fact that such contextual analysis can effectively make market analysis and strategic planning within the company (Grant, 2016). These frameworks were chosen over other business models such as Marketing Mix (7Ps) due to the fact it best addresses the strategy to take on the company growth and expansion in the market.

SWOT analysis provides understanding of Alva-Vista internal strength and weaknesses as well as the external opportunities and threats. This tool is simple to use and has a broader range of applicability making it the necessary strategy for assessment of the organisation, aligning the company capabilities and resources with market opportunities. PESTLE analysis examines the macro environment factors - policy, economy, society, technology, legal and ecology that impact the sea farming industry particularly on the export of crayfish (Lucid, 2019). Given the international nature of Alva-Vista business, understanding such factors is highly necessary.

The Ansoff Matrix is a valuable tool to point out the growth plan through market development, product development, market penetration and diversification. This strategy offers a systematic method to point out several avenues of growth, making sure that they align with the strategic aim of Alva-Vista and preparing the company to extend its market to be among the top of their competitors (Yin, 2019).

The Porter Five Forces framework examines the competitive forces present in the sectors which entail the negotiating power of the suppliers and buyers, potential for new entry, the level of rivalry within industry, and the danger of substitutes. This framework enabled Alva-Vista to formulate strategies and competitive dynamics to confront any threats within a competitive market (Mind Tools, 2022).

Lastly the Business Model Canvas presents a table on Alva-Vista key components such as client groups, channels, value proposition, and income streams. This tool is especially necessary in ensuring that Alva-Vista operational model aligns with its objective, thereby accomplishing financial targets and enabling a constant approach to providing value among the customers (BusinessDay, 2023).

When it comes to other alternatives, strategic planning is not that essential in carrying out plans for the Alva-Vista business. For example Marketing Mix which consist of 7ps, Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process and Physical Evidence provide tactical approach rather than strategic (Hanlon, 2023). Hence it can only define the short term goal of a business. However, what the business plan of Alva-Vista is looking for is the long term goal in the next five years.

The chosen business models in carrying out strategic planning for Alva-Vista enabled an informed decision making process with the aim of increasing the shareholders' value through expanding into new markets, achieving operational excellence and sustainable growth.

4.0 Strategic Plan for the Next Five Years

The business plan presents a growth strategy and its direction for Alva-Visa Crayfish within the next five years. The main aim is to increase the shareholder value which can be done by achieving a sustainable growth in profit. The primary objective is to not just enhance its operational

efficiency but achieve sustainable growth with the ultimate goal of becoming the number one in the Nigeria seafood industry among other competitors, which can be done so by promoting innovation, investing in infrastructure, and utilising market knowledge. This business strategy will without doubt help the company take advantage of new opportunities and overcome obstacles.

By defining its shareholders value entails to enduring growth of profit, which will eventually result in enhanced financial gains among the shareholders. This will encompass improved profitability through streamlined operation, sustained long-term growth and appreciation of stock prices, augmented revenue from market development which ensure stable appreciation and dividends of stock prices. The objective is to optimise financial gain while upholding the company's ability to endure and compete in any situation it's found itself in (McSweeney, 2008).

The five years plan for Alva-Vista entail of the following objective to enhance the shareholder value:

1. Expansion of Infrastructure:

- Erect 8 additional ponds, bringing the total to 12, in order to increase the manufacturing capacity.
- Conduct a drilling operation to create a borehole and subsequently install a water tank in order to establish a dependable water source for the fish farm.
- Deploy a greenhouse system to regulate temperatures and maximise fish cultivation efficiency.
- Acquire refrigerated vehicles (Cold room Vehicles) to expedite distribution throughout the country.

2. Market Penetration:

- Utilise market intelligence to identify crucial target categories and customise offerings to fulfil unique requirements.
- Formulate strategies and alliances with retailers, restaurants, key distributors, and direct consumers to enhance market penetration.
- Allocate resources towards promotional and marketing endeavours in order to improve the awareness of the company product and establish a unique identity in the market setting itself apart from other competition in the seafood industry.

3. Product Diversification:

- Investigate possibilities for extending the range of products beyond crayfish, taking advantage of growing trends and consumer preferences.
- Perform market research to uncover prospective new product categories and evaluate their viability and market demand.

4. Operational Efficiency:

- Employ cost-efficient production methods to maximise resource utilisation and minimise waste.
- Allocate resources towards the use of advanced technology and automation systems in order to optimise operational processes and enhance overall productivity.
- Consistently observe and assess performance indicators to pinpoint areas that need enhancement and execute necessary measures to rectify them.

5. Quality Assurance:

- Enforce stringent quality control protocols to ensure product integrity and adhere to global standards.

- Acquire pertinent certificates and accreditations to bolster credibility and gain entry to high-end markets.

6. Sustainability:

- Follow sustainable fishing methods to guarantee the enduring sustainability of crayfish populations and save the environment.

5.0 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Several key performance indicators are necessary to be adopted in Alva-Vista in order to measure the degree to which stakeholder value is being enhanced. This includes, increase in export revenue, customer satisfaction index (CSI), market penetration rate, employment generation, foreign exchange earnings, efficiency improvements, compliance rate and brand awareness

KPI	Measure	5-Years Target
Increase in Export Revenue	$(CurrRev - PrevRev) / PrevRev \times 100$	20%
Customer Satisfaction Index	$SatResp / TotalResp \times 100$	90%
Market Penetration Rate	$Cust / TargetMkt \times 100$	10%
Employment Generation	$(NewJobs - PrevJobs) / PrevJobs \times 100$	20%
Foreign Exchange Earnings	Tot Export Value $\times$ Exchange Rate	\$10,000 USD
Efficiency Improvements	$(OldTime - NewTime) / OldTime \times 100$	20%
Compliance Rate	$CompBatches / TotalBatches \times 100$	96%
Brand Awareness	$Brand - AwResp / TotalResp \times 100$	70%

Table 1: KPIs for Alva Vista business showcasing 5 years target

6.0 Financial Projections

Current Assets					
Description	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Cash, cash equivalents, and short-term investments	\$2,501	\$3,370	\$4,718	\$6,280	\$7,831
Restricted cash	\$1,060	\$945	\$811	\$652	\$696
Accounts receivable, net	\$901	\$943	\$962	\$1,006	\$1,059
Expendable parts and supplies inventories, net	\$190	\$190	\$190	\$190	\$190
Deferred income taxes, net	\$370	\$370	\$370	\$370	\$370
Prepaid expenses and other	\$492	\$496	\$492	\$596	\$590
Total Current Assets	\$5,514	\$6,314	\$7,543	\$9,094	\$10,736
Property and Equipment					
Description	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Crayfish harvesting and processing equipment	\$17,926	\$18,685	\$19,684	\$21,266	\$22,190
Accumulated depreciation	(\$6,814)	(\$7,648)	(\$8,519)	(\$9,484)	(\$10,485)
Crayfish harvesting and processing equipment, net	\$11,112	\$11,037	\$11,165	\$11,782	\$11,705
Packaging and shipping equipment	\$467	\$500	\$500	\$500	\$500
Accumulated amortization	(\$151)	(\$250)	(\$337)	(\$423)	(\$500)
Packaging and shipping equipment, net	\$316	\$250	\$163	\$77	-
Crayfish storage facilities	\$4,716	\$4,991	\$5,266	\$5,566	\$5,866
Accumulated depreciation	(\$2,957)	(\$3,151)	(\$3,339)	(\$3,533)	(\$3,731)
Crayfish storage facilities, net	\$1,759	\$1,840	\$1,927	\$2,033	\$2,135
Total Property and Equipment, net	\$13,187	\$13,127	\$13,255	\$13,892	\$13,840
Other Assets					
Description	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Brand and Trademarks	\$227	\$227	\$227	\$227	\$227
Operating licenses and other intangibles, net	\$82	\$82	\$82	\$82	\$82
Other noncurrent assets	\$1,113	\$1,149	\$1,182	\$1,202	\$1,202
Total Other Assets	\$1,422	\$1,458	\$1,491	\$1,511	\$1,511
Current Liabilities					
Description	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Current maturities of long-term debt and capital leases	\$1,301	\$716	\$389	\$1,340	\$1,402
Accounts payable	\$1,634	\$1,661	\$1,670	\$1,692	\$1,686
Crayfish transportation liability	\$1,861	\$1,966	\$2,115	\$2,266	\$2,424
Taxes payable	\$551	\$530	\$524	\$519	\$518
Accrued salaries and related benefits	\$408	\$1,078	\$1,215	\$1,255	\$1,354
Total Current Liabilities	\$5,755	\$5,951	\$5,913	\$7,072	\$7,384

Table 2: Projected Consolidated Balance Sheets of Alva Vista

Statement of Operation	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Operating Revenue					
Crayfish Sales	\$15,698	\$16,788	\$17,914	\$18,777	\$19,834
Cargo	\$494	\$546	\$579	\$630	\$655
Other, net	\$1,154	\$1,181	\$1,197	\$1,240	\$1,272
Total operating revenue	\$17,346	\$18,515	\$19,690	\$20,647	\$21,761
Operating Expenses					
Crayfish Harvesting & Processing	\$4,344	\$4,235	\$4,413	\$4,762	\$5,131
Salaries and related costs	\$4,063	\$3,626	\$3,633	\$3,799	\$3,936
Shipping and Handling	\$2,689	\$3,115	\$3,262	\$3,472	\$3,683
Depreciation and amortization	\$1,199	\$1,127	\$1,147	\$1,244	\$1,277
Marketing Expenses	\$1,041	\$1,145	\$1,081	\$1,033	\$1,001
Sales Commissions	\$879	\$897	\$974	\$1,037	\$1,096
Warehouse Rent	\$773	\$726	\$735	\$740	\$747
Equipment Maintenance	\$740	\$724	\$804	\$807	\$825
Packaging Supplies	\$324	\$327	\$361	\$391	\$409
Utilities	\$306	\$300	\$331	\$319	\$309
Labor Costs	\$2,500,000	\$3,000,000	\$3,500,000	\$4,000,000	\$4,500,000
Raw Materials	\$1,000,000	\$1,500,000	\$2,000,000	\$2,500,000	\$3,000,000
Transportation Costs	\$700,000	\$800,000	\$900,000	\$1,000,000	\$1,100,000
Other Miscellaneous	\$200,000	\$250,000	\$300,000	\$350,000	\$400,000
Subtotal	\$17,053	\$16,899	\$17,382	\$18,231	\$19,019
Profit sharing	-	\$196	\$329	\$363	\$457
Total Operating Expenses	\$5,200,000	\$6,550,000	\$8,000,000	\$9,250,000	\$10,600,000
Operating Income	\$293	\$1,420	\$1,979	\$2,053	\$2,285
Other Income/(Expense)					
Interest expense	(\$889)	(\$808)	(\$763)	(\$778)	(\$767)
Less: capitalized interest	\$8	\$14	\$21	\$10	\$5
Interest income	\$175	\$190	\$234	\$301	\$376
Miscellaneous income	(\$12)	-	-	-	-
Total Other Income/(Expense)	(\$718)	(\$604)	(\$508)	(\$467)	(\$386)
(Loss) Income Before Taxes	(\$425)	\$816	\$1,471	\$1,586	\$1,899
Income taxes, net	\$40	(\$360)	(\$552)	(\$595)	(\$711)
Net (loss) income	(\$385)	\$456	\$919	\$991	\$1,188

Table 3: Projected Consolidated Statement of Operations of Alva-Vista

Cash flows	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Cash Flows From Operating Activities:					
Net (loss) income	\$(385)	\$456	\$919	\$991	\$1,188
Depreciation and amortization	\$1,199	\$1,127	\$1,147	\$1,244	\$1,277
Rental expense in excess of (less than) payments	\$109	\$(30)	\$(95)	\$(1)	\$14
Pension, postretirement, postemployment expense in excess of payment	\$405	\$12	\$30	\$2	\$(18)
Other operating cashflow	\$(58)	-	-	-	-
Changes in certain current assets and liabilities:					
Increase in receivables	\$(137)	\$(42)	\$(18)	\$(45)	\$(52)
Decrease (increase) in other current assets	\$15	\$(19)	\$(28)	\$(124)	\$6
Increase in crayfish transportation liability	\$149	\$105	\$149	\$151	\$158
Utilization of federal NOLs	-	\$360	\$520	\$562	\$672
Increase in other AP and accrued expense	\$135	\$166	\$135	\$60	\$92
Increase in other noncurrent liability	\$42	\$18	\$6	\$12	\$14
Increase (decrease) in STC liabilities	\$65	\$(100)	-	-	-
Other, net	\$70	-	-	-	-
Net cash provided by operating activities	\$1,609	\$2,053	\$2,765	\$2,852	\$3,351
Cash Flows From Investing Activities:					
Crayfish harvesting and processing equipment additions, including advances net	\$(233)	\$(758)	\$(999)	\$(1,581)	\$(929)
Ground property and equipment additions	\$(138)	\$(275)	\$(275)	\$(300)	\$(300)
Proceeds from sale of equipment	\$34	-	-	-	-
(Increase) decrease in restricted cash	\$(29)	\$115	\$135	\$159	\$(44)
Other investing, net	\$6	-	-	-	-
Net cash used in investing activities	\$(360)	\$(918)	\$(1,139)	\$(1,722)	\$(1,273)
Free Cash Flow	\$1,249	\$1,135	\$1,626	\$1,130	\$2,078
Cash Flows From Financing Activities:					
Payments on long-term and capital lease obligations	\$(595)	\$(2,508)	\$(822)	\$(492)	\$(1,440)
Issuance of other long-term obligations	-	\$2,242	\$544	\$924	\$913
Other financing, net	\$(5)	-	-	-	-
Net cash (used in) provided by financing activities	\$(600)	\$(266)	\$(278)	\$432	\$(527)
Net increase in cash & cash equivalents	\$649	\$869	\$1,348	\$1,562	\$1,551
Cash & cash equivalents at beginning of period	\$1,852	\$2,501	\$3,370	\$4,718	\$6,280
Cash & cash equivalents at end of period	\$2,501	\$3,370	\$4,718	\$6,280	\$7,831

Table 4: Consolidated Statement of Cash Flows of Alva-Vista

7.0 Risk Assessment

1. Seasonal Variability in Crayfish Availability

Risk: Seasonal fluctuations in crayfish availability can disrupt supply chains and affect production schedules, leading to inefficiencies and potential revenue loss (Msangameno & Mangora, 2016).

Fig 1: Seasonal variation of crayfish

Source: Stearns and Serfass (2011)

Mitigation Strategies:

- **Diversify Supply Sources:** Collaborate with many suppliers from various regions to minimise the consequences of localised shortages.
- **Inventory Management:** Deploy sophisticated inventory management systems to efficiently align supply and demand.
- **Investment in Aquaculture:** Carry out the allocation of funds pertaining to the development of crayfish farming and aquaculture techniques to achieve steady and reliable supply at any season of the year.
- **Diversify Supply Sources:** Partner with suppliers in several locations in order to mitigate the impartation of localised shortages.
- **Inventory Management:** Implement advanced inventory management systems to make an effective balance of both demand and supply.

2. Ensuring Quality Control and Compliance

Risk: Insufficient quality control can result in the production of subpar goods that do not fulfil global export criteria, thereby harming the company's standing and leading to financial setbacks (Benyahkoub et al, 2021).

Mitigation Strategies:

- **Robust Quality Control Systems:** Implement rigorous quality control methods at each level of processing, starting from sourcing and extending to packing.
- **Certifications and Training:** Acquire global certifications such as ISO and HACCP, and deliver continuous training to employees to uphold exceptional standards.
- **Routine Audits:** Perform internal and external periodic audits to ensure verification of adherence to quality standards and regulatory obligations.

3. Logistics and Distribution Challenges

Risk: Poor distribution and logistics can consequently lead to increased cost, compromise product quality and delay in the supply of goods to the consumers (Prime Group, 2021).

Mitigation Strategies:

- **Strategic Partnerships:** Partners with logistics and distribution companies which are reliable in terms of having professional expertise in logistics of perishable goods.
- **Cold Chain Infrastructure:** Invest in cold chain logistics which encompasses cold van, and cold warehouse to ensure the crayfish products remain fresh for longer periods of time.

4. Regulatory and Trade Barriers

Risk: Navigating complex export regulations and trade barriers in the global market can result in administrative burden and compliance challenges (Benyahkoub et al., 2021).

Mitigation Strategies:

- **Regulatory Expertise:** Employ or consult with regulatory experts to stay informed about the latest export regulations and compliance requirements.
- **Market Research:** Perform market research to gain extensive knowledge in the regulatory environment of the target export market.
- **Advocacy and Networking:** Advocate for favourable trade policies and be informed pertaining to regulatory changes by actively participating in industry associations and government bodies.

5. Competition from Established Exporters

Risk: Rivalry from established seafood industry negatively impacts the profit and share of a business (Tran et al., 2021).

Mitigation Strategies:

- **Differentiation:** Focus on differentiating Alva-Vista products among other rivals by pointing out superior quality, sustainable practices and unique packaging.
- **Brand Building:** Implement marketing initiatives to actively involve the target audience and raise awareness of the product of Alva-Vista.
- **Customer Connections:** Maintain and strengthen a good relationship with existing clients while providing quality products to them.

6. Economic Instability and Currency Fluctuations

Risk: The company financial profitability and planning of the company can be affected due to the currency fluctuation and economic uncertainty in Nigeria (Udeze et al., 2021).

Fig 2: Fluctuation in the exchange rate from 1990 - 2020

Source: Kechi and Anthony (2020)

Mitigation Strategies:

- **Hedging:** Utilise financial instruments such as futures to minimise the company's financial risk while there is an increase in the foreign exchange rates.
- **Diversification:** Diversify the customer in accordance with their location in order to spread economic risk.
- **Flexible Pricing:** Adopt a strategy of flexible pricing which can be altered based on the economic situation and the fluctuations of currency.

7. Environmental and Climate Change

Risk: Environmental changes and climate risks can impact crayfish habitats, affecting harvest yields and long-term sustainability (Maulu et al., 2021).

Fig 3: Impact of climate change on tropical and subtropical fishing and coastal habitats.

Source: Danylchuk et al (2022)

Mitigation Strategies

- **Sustainable Practices:** Adopt the practices of sustainable fishing to carry out the protection of the habitat of crayfish as well as their populace.
- **Environmental Monitoring:** Implement a system in order to look out for the situation of the environment and take action against any negative changes that will disturb the production flow of crayfish.
- **Research and Development:** Invest in research and development that aim at carrying out the cultivation of robust crayfish species and implementing sustainable aquaculture.

8 Technology Adoption and Innovation

Risk: Falling to engage in innovation and embrace technologies will definitely result in a decline in competitive advantage and operational inefficiencies (Ogah et al., 2022).

Mitigation Strategies

- **Continuous Improvement:** Promote a culture of ongoing innovation and development throughout the organisation.
- **Investment in Technology:** Invest in cutting-edge packaging and processing technology to improve product quality and optimise efficiency.
- **Training and Development:** Continuously provide training to staff to be updated on the use of new technology in seafood production.

9.0 Recommendation

The subsequent recommendation is put forth to point out the trajectory strategy Alva-Vista Crayfish Export should adopt in order for there to be a sustainable expansion of the business. The recommendations are as follows:

1. Alva-Vista should expand by providing several options of products to the customer. e.g. The business shouldn't just focus on the export of just smoked or fresh crayfish alone, but other items like crayfish maggi, crayfish pasta etc. By diversifying this product people will be given several options to choose the product they need (CFI, 2022).
2. Alva-Vista should expand its market in countries where there are several Nigerians immigrants and target exporting goods to them. As Nigerians overseas buying their local goods will definitely help propels a positive cycle that contributes considerably to the overall economic growth of their country (Ogungbe, 2024).
3. Rather than Alva-Vista having only concern with the export of crayfish it should adopt sustainable practices like eliminating water pollution. This approach will not only preserve the life of fish in general but enhance the organisation's reputation for aiding the productivity of fish (Amit, 2023).

4. Alva-Vista should implement a continuous training initiative to broaden the staff knowledge. For example there should be training on adopting the use of any current technology such as Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS) to boost the productivity of crayfish (Marzuki et al., 2018).

9.0 Conclusion

Alva-Vista Crayfish Export is in a favourable position to take advantage of Nigeria's significant crayfish production and satisfy the increasing worldwide need for top-notch seafood. The company intends to assure a regular supply of high-quality crayfish products by tackling industry difficulties such as fragmented supply chains and uneven quality, and by developing a vertically integrated business strategy. The financial estimates suggest a favourable picture, with a substantial expansion in production capacity and profitability anticipated in the next five years.

Through a strong emphasis on operational efficiency, sustainability, and strategic market expansion, Alva-Vista Crayfish Export has the capacity to position itself as a prominent participant in the global seafood market. This would not only be a significant employment prospect but also contribute to the development of the agricultural sector within Nigeria. The company has a well-equipped strategic plan which includes strategies for managing risks effectively and penetrating into the new market. This positions the business for increased value for its shareholders and long-term success.

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Appendix 1: Job Advertisement

JOB DESCRIPTION

1. Crayfish Farm Manager:

Qualifications:

- Bachelor's degree in Aquaculture, Fisheries, Biology, or related field.
- Minimum of 5 years of experience in aquaculture, with specific experience in crayfish farming preferred.
- Strong leadership and management skills, with the ability to effectively supervise a team.
- Knowledge of aquaculture practices, water quality management, and disease prevention techniques.
- Excellent problem-solving abilities and attention to detail.
- Good communication skills and the ability to collaborate with internal teams and external partners.
- Familiarity with regulatory requirements and environmental regulations related to aquaculture operations.

2. Crayfish Processing Supervisor:

Qualifications:

- Bachelor's degree in Food Science, Fisheries Technology, or related field.
- Minimum of 3 years of experience in food processing, preferably in seafood processing.
- Knowledge of food safety standards and regulations, including HACCP and GMP.
- Experience operating and maintaining processing equipment, such as boilers, steamers, and packaging machinery.
- Strong leadership and supervisory skills, with the ability to motivate and manage a team.
- Attention to detail and a commitment to maintaining product quality and consistency.
- Good organizational and time management skills, with the ability to prioritize tasks in a fast-paced environment.
- Knowledge of basic maintenance procedures and troubleshooting techniques for processing equipment.

3. Sales and Marketing Manager:

Qualifications:

- Bachelor's degree in Marketing, Business Administration, or related field. MBA preferred.
- Minimum of 5 years of experience in sales and marketing, with a focus on food or agricultural products.
- Proven track record of success in developing and implementing sales strategies that drive revenue growth.
- Strong negotiation and relationship-building skills, with the ability to cultivate partnerships with key stakeholders.
- Excellent communication skills, both written and verbal, with the ability to present ideas effectively to internal and external audiences.
- Analytical mindset with the ability to interpret sales data and market trends to inform decision-making.
- Experience leading and mentoring a sales team, with a focus on coaching and development.
- Knowledge of international trade regulations and experience with export sales preferred.

To apply for any of the positions listed above, please send your resume/CV along with a cover letter to AlvaVistaCrayfishExport@gmail.com. Please use the job role you are applying for as the subject of your email.

These job posts give a clear outline of the skills, education level and experience needed for various job roles within the Alva-Visa Crayfish Export industry.

Appendix 2: Client Testimonials

Adewale A., Lagos Seafood Palace's Executive Chef

"It is essential for an executive chef to source the best ingredients. We always receive the freshest crayfish from Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company, which enhances the flavour of our meals. They are our go-to source for crayfish because of their dependability."

Ngozi O., Owner, Niger Delta Crayfish Delight

"Quality is a given when operating a business that specialises in crayfish. Our expectations are exceeded by Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company's excellent crayfish, which is consistently supplied on schedule. They are essential to our success."

Babatunde M., West African Seafood Distributors, Import Manager

"We at West African Seafood Distributors take great satisfaction in providing our customers with the greatest seafood. Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company is a trusted supply chain partner since they regularly provide high-quality crayfish."

Chinyere E., Owner, of Crayfish Market by the Ocean

"The freshest crayfish is what our customers want, and Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company always meets their needs. Our customers love their crayfish, and they stand out for their professionalism. Being in business with them makes us proud."

Oluwafemi B., The head buyer at Coastal Seafood Emporium

"Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company is distinguished by their dedication to dependability and quality. Their crawfish constantly satisfies our requirements and leaves our customers happy by being delicious and fresh. They are a reliable business partner for us."

Adebayo F., Lagoon View Restaurant Owner and Chef

"We receive crawfish from Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company that are of unmatched quality. Their prompt deliveries and meticulous attention to detail guarantee that we can always provide our customers with the best seafood. They are crucial to our accomplishments."

Nkechi I., Atlantic Ocean Foods purchasing manager

"It has been a joy doing business with Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company. They always have the best crawfish, and their customer service is outstanding. We value their dependability and commitment to excellence."

Chukwuemeka N., Head Chef, Savoury Flavours Kitchen

"We are able to prepare dishes that our guests will remember because Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company supplies us with the freshest crawfish on a regular basis. Our preferred crawfish supplier is them because of their professionalism and attention to detail."

Aisha S, Manager of Seaside Delights Market

"Crayfish from Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company are a market favourite at Seaside Delights. They stand out for their quality and reliability, and they provide great customer service. We appreciate their collaboration"

Appendix 3: Award and Certificate

Certificate of Excellence

This is to certify that

Alva-Vista Crayfish Export Company

Has been recognized as the Best Researcher in the field of Crayfish Production Optimization in acknowledgement of their outstanding dedication, innovative research methodologies and significant contribution to advancing the techniques for increasing Crayfish yields.

Presented by:

Maduemezie Emeka

CEO, Athena Research Institute of Nigeria

Date: May 15, 2022

This certificate serves as a proof of the remarkable contribution that Alva-Vista has made in research and development towards the increase in productivity of crayfish using certain techniques.

Appendix 4: KPIs Formula

1. Increase in Export Revenue:

Formula: Increase in Export Revenue (%) =

$$\left(\frac{\text{Revenue In The Current Period} - \text{Revenue In The Previous Period}}{\text{Revenue In The Previous Period}} \right) \times 100$$

Target: Increase in Export Revenue (%) = $\left(\frac{1,200,000 - 1,000,000}{1,000,000} \right) \times 100 = 20\%$

2. Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI):

Formula: $CSI (\%) = \left(\frac{\text{Total Satisfied Responded}}{\text{Total Responded}} \right) \times 100$

Target: $CSI (\%) = \left(\frac{450}{500} \right) \times 100 = 90\%$

3. Market Penetration Rate:

Formula: $Market Penetration Rate (\%) = \left(\frac{\text{Number of Customers}}{\text{Total Targets Market}} \right) \times 100$

Target: $Market Penetration Rate (\%) = \left(\frac{5,000}{50,000} \right) \times 100 = 10\%$

4. Employment Generation:

Formula: $Employment Growth (\%) = \left(\frac{\text{New Jobs Created} - \text{Jobs in the Previous Period}}{\text{Jobs in the Previous Period}} \right) \times 100$

Target: $Employment Growth (\%) = \left(\frac{250 - 200}{200} \right) \times 100 = 20\%$

5. Foreign Exchange Earnings:

Formula: Foreign Exchange Earnings (\$) = Total Export Value in Local Currency × Exchange Rate

Target: Foreign Exchange Earnings (\$) = $5,000,000 \times \frac{1}{500} = 10,000\text{USD}$

6. Efficiency Improvements:

Formula: *Efficiency Improvement (%)* = $\left(\frac{\text{Old Processing Time} - \text{New Processing Time}}{\text{Old Processing Time}} \right) \times 100$

Target: *Efficiency Improvement (%)* = $\left(\frac{10-8}{10} \right) \times 100 = 20\%$

7. Compliance Rate:

Formula: *Compliance Rate (%)* = $\left(\frac{\text{Number of Compliance Batches}}{\text{Total Batches}} \right) \times 100$

Target: *Compliance Rate (%)* = $\left(\frac{480}{500} \right) \times 100 = 96\%$

8. Brand Awareness:

Formula: *Brand Awareness (%)* = $\left(\frac{\text{Survey Respondent of the Brand}}{\text{Total Survey Respondent}} \right) \times 100$

Target: *Brand Awareness (%)* = $\left(\frac{700}{1,000} \right) \times 100 = 70\%$